

ISSUES OF USING THE IPO MECHANISM IN THE INVESTMENT ACTIVITIES OF JOINT-STOCK COMPANIES

Azizbek Abdurashidovich Shomirov

Associate Professor of the Department
of “Valuation and Investment”, Ph.D.
Tashkent Financial University, Uzbekistan

Abstract: This article explores and analyzes the need for an IPO mechanism to improve the financial performance of joint stock companies. The IPO is being studied, that is, the content of a public offering of shares, its importance and stages of implementation, as well as its advantages and disadvantages in attracting investment to joint stock companies operating in our country. Analyzed the IPO of large companies in world and domestic practice. The article identifies problems in this area and develops the author's proposals and recommendations on them.

Key words: IPO, public offering, Road Show, joint stock companies, companies, prospectus, raising capital, stock market, capital market.

INTRODUCTION. Regardless of the sphere in which joint-stock companies operate in the country, the allocation of additional financial resources, including the attraction of foreign investment, remains an important task. One of the most modern ways to attract investment in joint-stock companies is to use the IPO mechanism. As a legal basis for the work to be done in this regard, we certainly refer to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 7, 2017 "On the Strategy for further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan" PF-4947 of April 29, 2019 [1]. It is necessary to cite the Resolution No. PK-4300 [2] "On measures to further improve the mechanisms for attracting foreign direct investment in the economy of the Republic." These normative documents set out the following important tasks.

In particular:

- Development of the concept of medium-term and long-term development of the financial market of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the medium and long term, aimed at attracting capital and developing the financial market as an alternative source of free funds of enterprises, financial institutions and the population. IPO), to ensure their access to foreign capital markets;

- documenting the documents of business entities on the acquisition of shares and stakes of enterprises that have a leading position in creating an effective competitive environment for industries and achieving a gradual reduction of the monopoly in the market of goods and services;

- sale of state-owned shares (stakes) in the charter capital of chemical and oil and gas industries, business entities in the field of mechanical engineering, banking and insurance organizations;

- Development of ready investment proposals to attract foreign direct investment.

One of the most important of these tasks, of course, is the IPO- (Initial public offering) mechanism, which serves to increase the prestige of joint stock companies. This is because today the continuous involvement of joint-stock companies in financial resources is directly proportional to the development of the Uzbek securities market, in mathematical terms.

In the middle of our research, we studied the opinions of leading global and local economists on the IPO mechanism, which is interpreted as "initial public offering". At the same time, the term "public offering" implies the free trade of shares of joint-stock companies with a large number of institutional and private investors. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Securities Market", adopted on June 3, 2015, defines the

public offering of securities as an open subscription to an unlimited number of investors using advertising [3]. According to Doctor of Economics, Professor S. Elmirzaev, "IPO means the first time the issuer's shares are sold on the open market" [4].

According to a study by foreign economists Allen Michel and Jacob Oded, the IPO is "one of the most important events in the IPO's existence, and its use is an additional financial resource to expand the activities of young and new companies in the future."

In another study, leading foreign economists Leonella Gori and Emanuele Teti described the IPO as a "significant accumulation of funds for strategic investment during the company's lifetime." A. According to Zyglin, "an IPO is a public offering of a company's shares on a stock exchange, which allows millions of people around the world to buy its shares and publicize the company itself." According to O. Lomontatidze, M. Lvova, A. Bolotin, "IPO (Initial Public Offering) is the initial public offering of shares of a company for sale to a wide range of buyers. This means that the company will list its shares on the stock exchange for the first time and offer them to an unlimited number of buyers." [8] According to Doctor of Economics, Professor E. Zhukov, "IPO is a type of initial public offering, in the process of which new shares of the company are constantly sold." [9] According to Investopedia, "Initial public offering (IPO) is the process by which a private corporation issues new shares to be offered for sale to the public." [10]

Based on the above, it should be noted that the IPO applies only to the most common type of securities per share, providing for the public sale of shares of the company on the stock market.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY. The main purpose of this study is to use the IPO mechanism to increase the efficiency of joint-stock companies and optimize the

process of attracting investment, as well as to conduct scientific and practical proposals for the initial public offering of shares in the stock market. The methods of comparison, grouping and SWOT analysis were widely used in the research process. As a result of the study, scientific and practical proposals were developed on measures to apply the IPO mechanism to increase the efficiency of joint-stock companies and optimize the process of attracting investment.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS. Today, the development of the securities market in Uzbekistan is associated with the growing role of financing the activities of joint-stock companies. At the same time, one of the most popular and rapidly developing forms of investment financing is the initial placement of these shares. Despite the fact that the world is beginning to be used in practice, and mass deployment is widely used in developed countries, in our country this process is a relatively new financial mechanism, so it is necessary to study it more deeply.

First of all, we will see the main purpose of using the IPO mechanism in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1. The main purpose of the initial public offering of shares of joint-stock companies¹

¹Formed by the author

As can be seen from Figure 1, when companies attract investment, they publicly place their shares on the stock market through an IPO, which in turn not only attracts additional financial resources to joint stock companies, but also contributes to the development of the stock market, including the capital market. After defining the purpose of the IPO, we will now study the initial stages of public placement. That is, the initial public offering of shares of companies is carried out at the following stages:

1. Preliminary preparation. Companies must meet certain requirements (usually 1-2 years) prior to the initial public offering of their shares. In particular, well-designed business plans and regular preparation of financial statements are required for joint-stock companies to conduct an IPO.

2. Forming a team for the IPO. At this stage, the company will form a team that will help to conduct the IPO. There is an audit company, an investment bank and a legal aid company. This community should hold a general meeting 1-2 months before submitting the documents to the Securities Commission. During the meeting, all members of the group will be identified areas of responsibility, the schedule and schedule of the IPO. The IPO will officially start after all members of the team close the meeting.

3. Drawing up an issue prospectus. This process is a key tool in attracting investors to the company. It should be noted that the issue prospectus is required to provide the most complete and transparent information about the company issuing shares. As a rule, the issue prospectus includes financial statements for the last five years, information about the target audience, key competitors, development prospects and plans, as well as the characteristics of management staff. At the same time, the

investment bank conducts an in-depth analysis of the issuer, carefully examines all available information, and then identifies certain cases that are included in the documents and sent to the investor by a legal partner and the auditor. Prior to the issuance of the final version of the issue prospectus, it should be inspected by the Securities Commission. At this stage, the underwriter determines which of the investment partners will distribute this issue prospectus to potential customers. The final issue prospectus will be sent to investors for review.

4. Road Show Passage. Road Show events and gatherings in various cities are attended by investors, as well as large depositors such as banks, various funds and insurance corporations. At this time, it is very important to motivate potential customers to buy shares in the company. The Road Show usually lasts about a month. At the Road Show, the company's management will have to hold at least two meetings every day with potential buyers of securities. This is a very important stage in the preparation of the IPO, and at this stage the underwriter begins to create a book of orders. After the Road Show, the company's founders met with representatives of the investment bank to confirm the volume of shares issued, as well as the price offered to investors. The number of securities and their value are formed on the basis of a preliminary assessment of the demand for them. After the approval of prices, the final version of the issue prospectus and information on price correction are sent to the print media, which is then approved by the founders and the securities are distributed to clients.

5. Starting the sale of securities. Once the share price is clearly set and confirmed, the IPO will be announced (as a rule, it will be announced publicly after all trades on the stock exchange are closed). The securities begin to be distributed among the underwriters and their partners. The sale of shares begins the next day at the same

time as the stock exchange. At this stage, the leading investment bank must ensure the stability of the securities and monitor the sales process.

6. Make a deal. If a company transfers a block of shares to its underwriter, and the underwriter, in turn, transfers the money in full to the company's account, the transaction is considered completed (the process usually takes three days). One week after the end of the deal, the public offer will be officially announced as successful, and twenty-five days after the start of the IPO, the period of silence will end. Only after this period, community members will have the right to make a public statement about the company's forecast price, as well as to recommend to potential investors to buy securities.

In the above-mentioned stages, joint-stock companies may initially publicly place their shares, and as a result may have additional financial resources. Kuyid

Table 1

SWOT analysis of the IPO mechanism ²

Advantages (Strengths)	Opportunities
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • attracting large sums of money; • increasing the resilience of the financial structure; • reduction of borrowed funds; • achieving high liquidity through share capital; • the company's reputation, recognition and reputation; • there is no risk in attracting capital; • The market value of the company is determined. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Possibility of optimal distribution of property; • Capacity building of the company's negotiation capacity; • Achieving long-term development goals; • Achieving high competitiveness in the market; • Incentivize managers and employees by creating opportunities to buy company shares.
Disadvantages (Weaknesses)	Dangerous aspects

² Formed by the author.

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • public disclosure of information; • high emission costs. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low stock prices; • Excessive volume of large companies.
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From Table 1 above, we can conclude that the method of using the IPO mechanism to attract additional financial resources to joint-stock companies, including investments, has its advantages and disadvantages, as well as other methods. However, it should be noted that the advantages of the initial public offering of shares will have a positive impact on its future activities, market position and popularity of the company.

As a result of our research, we analyzed a number of companies in the world that have floated their shares through IPOs to major stock exchanges. In particular, Figure 2 below shows the IPOs of some of the world's largest companies.

Figure 2. The largest IPO transactions in the world, \$ 1 billion³

As we can see from Figure 2, the largest IPO held to date has been held by Saudi Aramco, a Saudi oil company. Saudi Aramco, which initially sold its shares to the Saudi Stock Exchange in 2019, will receive \$ 25.6 billion. In a bid to raise US \$ 1 billion, he set a new record for himself. The stock was valued at \$ 8.53 per share, valued at \$ 1.7 trillion. USD. In addition, Alibaba, the People's Republic of China, has invested more than \$ 25 billion in the three largest IPOs. It is worth noting that the Industrial and

³ Муаллиф томонидан шакллантирилди.

Commercial Bank of the People's Republic of China has raised US \$ 22.1 billion in capital gains in the amount of US \$ 22.1 billion.

In Uzbekistan, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan signed a decree on January 17, 2017 "On measures to accelerate the sale of women state property and simplify its procedures." urological (IPO) and Secondary (SPO) open bidding to the public audio and business entities. According to the Cabinet of Ministers Resolution of May 10, 2017 "On the organization of the public offering of shares on the stock exchange", the shares of JSC "Quartz" are to be tried in the IPO way. 4574934 pieces with a nominal value of 1715 soums from the volume of Dastlab Quartz JSC amounted to 7846.01 mln. The issue of ordinary shares was registered on October 2, 2017 and placed on the Tashkent Stock Exchange on December 5. The sale price per share is set at Rs 3,000 to Rs 9,900 and is set to take place on April 3, 2018. This is the first time in the history of the stock market that our country has carried out the first public offering of shares (IPO) method. According to the results of the IPO, "Quartz" JSC received an additional \$ 7523.81 million. has received a substantial turnover. Some of this funding is intended to cover the costs of IPO transfer. Modernization of the production capacity at the Kolgani enterprise has been spent on the installation of new modern equipment [10]. In addition to the Azerbaijan, the Cunicipation of Cunicipation of Cunicipation April 29, on January 29, the Caller Investment General of the United States of Ozhbekistan, is in the community of the community in the community of the community. In particular, according to this resolution, the shares of state-owned shares (shares) in the charter capital of the private companies that are being offered for sale to investors, including foreign investors, have been identified, and the shareholders will have a share of 100 shares. Namanganvino JSC, Kokon Ug-Moi JSC, Asaka UG JSC,

Kokon Mechanics Plant JSC, shareholders in the charter capital of state-owned assets of the Republic of Uzbekistan

The above research shows that today there are enough problems and controversial situations in attracting investments to joint-stock companies through the IPO mechanism. Examples include:

- First of all, not only non-economists, but also economists do not have a clear idea of what an IPO is;

- The purpose of the IPO among the representatives of joint-stock companies operating in the country is that they do not have clear strategies for its requirements and necessity, that is, they rely only on old methods of raising capital for their activities;

- Do not use foreign experience in conducting road shows;

- Weak implementation of legal and regulatory documents to reduce the state share in the charter capital of joint-stock companies through the initial public offering.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS. In conclusion, there are a number of pressing issues, especially problems in attracting investments to joint-stock companies of the country, the main reason for which is the lack of capital loans from commercial banks. We can emphasize that

It is expedient to implement the following proposals related to attracting investments in joint-stock companies:

1. It is necessary to ensure that the IPO mechanism is explained to the representatives of different fields through various means;

2. Joint-stock companies operating in our country should develop their own capital-raising strategy and, in turn, give high priority to the application of the IPO mechanism under this strategy;

3. Use of foreign experience in organizing Road Shows in IPOs;
4. It is necessary to strictly control the unconditional execution of normative and legal acts on reduction of the state share in the charter capital of joint-stock companies.

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